

New digital stressors :

- Social media pressure
- Cyberbullying
- privacy concerns
- Digital addiction

Adolescents need to be heard, develop positive thoughts and receive peer support

WHAT IS MENTAL HEALTH DISTRESS

Isolation, poor communication, vaccine fear

Harassment, stigmatisation

WELCOME TO

SMILE

We develop digital mental health solutions for young people.

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EU Contribution: € 6,018,376

15 partners from 9 European countries

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- 2 Self-assessment and Learning new skills through gamified scenarios

- 3 Be more resilient, have healthier lifestyle and promote your self-care

OUR VISION

is that the emerging methods and technologies of Gamification and AI are a real opportunity to boost mental health organisations, supplement diagnostic and treatment gaps and meet the SDGs as SDGs3 and the WHO Mental health action plan.

OUR AMBITION

is to empower the lived experience of youth with an emphasis on a recovery-oriented and psychosocial approach to mental health and well-being. The aim is to boost individuals' resilience towards stress while creating "benefits" both at the individual and society levels.

OUR SOLUTIONS

The Open knowledge Platform (OKP) will be at the heart of decreasing the risks of psychological distress and increasing awareness about mental health. The **gamified scenarios and AI-tools** will be the brain of self assessment, monitoring and care.

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<https://www.horizonsmile.eu/>

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